

Rethinking the Integration of Moral Values Education into South African Secondary School Curriculum

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Abstract

Kohlberg's theory of moral cognitive development is the theory that underpins this qualitative study. Integration of values education in the education system by the teachers remains an effective approach to address moral decadence. Ten lesson observations from five different schools and semi-structured interview were thematically analysed to present findings. Thus, the researchers adopted interpretivism in presentation and discussion of findings for the study. Findings revealed that moral education is viewed differently by teachers in its integration in schools. Some participants opined that some selected subjects should be used for the integration of moral values in South African schools. The teacher, however, decried lack of adequate training on the integration of moral values in learners. Hence, the study recommends adequate and regular training of teachers on classroom pedagogy of integrating moral values in learners through all the subjects. Appropriate rewards and punishment should be employed by the school system to promote appropriate values in learners. South African high schools should review and integrate contents of moral education into the curriculum for classroom instructional delivery. Teachers should endeavour to understand the full usage of learners' moral judgment competence, respect for every member of the community and moral cognition in an attempt to maximise the "Zone of proximal development" theory.

Introduction

Moral education is an important aspect of African philosophy (Lilian, 2018). Hence, it is critical to the moral upbringing of social group members in Africa. The school is a social system with the complimentary responsibility of raising learners with acceptable societal norms and values. The integration of value-based education is currently an international concern. Research indicates that education is regarded as a significant vehicle of inculcating values among children (Durdukoca, 2019). This is why values should be an integral component of the school Curriculum. In 2012, the South African Department of Education deliberately adopted the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS), which categorically aims at equipping learners with the knowledge, skills and values required for self-fulfilment, and practical parallels, regardless of their socio-economic context, race, gender, physical ability backgrounds (Department of Education, 2011). Hence, teachers are expected to integrate value education into teaching and learning methods (Hadi, 2015).

Hadi (2015) further suggests that a model is required to encourage the incorporation of good values into classroom sessions. Identifying an effective model for the teaching of good moral values is in line with the objectives of national education as outlined in the 1996 South African Constitution (DBE, 2011), which stresses, among other things, the importance of teaching core values that are deeply embedded in religious and national culture, and the need to respond to current demands for education. One of the key aims of worldwide education systems is to establish fundamental values in learners to prepare them, mould their character and actions to become useful, accountable, responsive and universal upright citizens in any society they find themselves (Shelly & Kusum, 2012; Fechter, 2014). Conversely, integration of values can be seen

as more than simply teaching learners only what is right and wrong, but as a means of fostering positive views of life among learners. Integration of values does not only emphasize the potentials learners can acquire with high academic accomplishments, but also with a strong association with societal values such as the power of wisdom, reverence, accountability, forgiveness, truthfulness, and solidarity for the absolute well-being of society (Abdullah, Hidayana, Kutunegara, & Indiyanto, 2019).

It is therefore imperative, that teachers in all subject areas consciously and intentionally consider the inclusion of values during all teaching and learning activities in schools. Such concerted efforts will reflect the holistic development of the learner, academically, spiritually and physically. Research has shown that the assimilation of moral values into education systems is a major concern for stakeholders in education, but as demonstrated by the widespread moral deterioration of school leavers in different parts of the world, it has not been well implemented (Durdukoca, 2019). Ugwuozor (2014) in his longitudinal study declares that lack of moral education from the education system is responsible for moral regression among learners and this lack of moral education is the curriculum deficiency in the country's current education systems. Similarly, some unethical causes, such as gender-based abuse, drug addiction and underage pregnancy, to highlight just a few social vices that adversely affect school learners in South African education system, necessitate for adequate and regular training of teachers (Ajani, 2019) in moulding learners with appropriate moral values. With this in mind, the researchers believe that school organisations need to reconsider creating an enabling atmosphere for moral teaching and learning, and the need for government to encourage curriculum designers to re-design school curriculum to accommodate the realities of today's upright moral personalities (Ugwuozor, 2014). Hence, there is a need for the school system to address social vices through the integration of Value-Based Education (VBE) in the curricula (Lilian, 2018). Studies have also shown that the impetus for teaching moral values in schools is to raise good, respectful and responsible learners.

There is no doubt that value education encourages social interactions, positive attitudes, appropriate behaviour and offer guidance about how individuals should behave in society and the world at large (Lovat, 2017). Furthermore, Hadi (2015) avers that the importance of values and morality is a necessary cypher in a cultured or civilized and just society we live. Moral education is significant in guiding our relationships with one another, in business and professional behaviour with friends and family. Chaitanya (2017) opines that the integration of values contributes to the development of children's moral judgment, imagination and reasoning. The ultimate aim of incorporating principles into the curriculum is to facilitate the needed revival of moral values in schools and society as a whole. Although the South African Constitution has enshrined values that need to be communicated and instilled in the lives of school learners, the country is still facing an intense moral crisis. This study, therefore, is an immediate response for the need to re-ignite moral values in South Africa to redress the value crisis. The Department of Education declares its intention to build values in schools as stipulated in its Manifesto on Values, Education and Democracy. In July 2000, an initiative called the Moral Regeneration Movement (MRM) was launched by the South African government to inform all parties responsible for youth education to enshrine fundamental values as stipulated by the South African Constitution (RSA, Parliament, 1996) and the Manifesto on Values in South African youths.

Evidence suggests, however, that these efforts and programmes were inadequate (De Wet, 2003). According to findings from a study conducted by De Wet (2003), crime in South African schools was indeed a problem as moral decadence. This implies that various form of indiscipline is demonstrated by the actions of both learners and teachers, and it is the primary cause of deterioration in South African schools' learning and educational culture. The loss in discipline, however, is not limited to South Africa only but a global phenomenon (Steyn et al., 2003). The focus of moral education is to integrate core values that can help learners develop positive areas for strength and remove the negative ones. It is believed that teaching of values provides a framework for the integration of values as alternatives for learners to consider their choices in life to avoid all kinds of social vices. The goal of integrating values into teaching subjects is to build a supportive atmosphere and emotions in learners to make them responsive citizens that can maximise all the three learning fields, in promoting peaceful coexistence and societal development.

Theoretical Framework

This research was driven by Kohlberg's moral development theory, which suggests that teenagers appear to assimilate moral values from others who are older than them, especially their parents and teachers who are well experienced in life than them (Simanowitz & Pearce, 2003). The theory further explains the necessity of imparting moral values in adolescents by the teachers in the school system. Harish (2011), Raley and Preyer (2010), and Winch and Gingel (2004) affirm in their studies that the absence of moral education from the school curriculum is a significant contribution to social decay. Tuckman and Monetti (2011), posit that learners who score low in moral judgment are likely to display destructive behaviour in school environments. This may cause disciplinary cases that may interfere with the academic performance of learners. Schools need to promote moral growth in this respect and facilitate moral development in learners. In other areas of learning, this is as critical as making learners grow.

The adoption of Kohlberg's (1984) theory of moral development into this study is to enhance value integration into learners in high schools to address growth in social decay in our societies. Kohlberg drew strength for this theory from Dewey's thoughts on Progressive Theory of Ethics as well as inspirations from Piaget's theory of Child Development. These two theories that strengthened Kohlberg's (1984) moral development make the theory one of the most appropriate theories in moral development. This theory promotes moral education in the education system through its main tenets. Kohlberg (1984) avers that the moral development of learners is closely connected to their cognitive development. Thus, the moral development of learners is driven by their cognitive development level. Integration of moral values is done in stages or phases which cannot be reversed. Learners' moral development in schools can be enhanced in teaching and learning activities by teachers for self-realization and social acceptance based on their active participation. The school as a social system plays a significant role in the moral development of learners. This supports Kohlberg's assertions for the development of moral values in stages that can be qualitatively monitored by teachers according to his three levels: pre-conventional level, conventional level and post-conventional level.

Furthermore, the emphasis on Kohlberg's theory is focused on the importance of the environment in the moral development of learners. The moral atmosphere must be aligned with the degree of moral maturity for the adolescent, and provide a framework in which the learner feels both protected and challenged. School as a social system can create the space for learners to acquire and develop the traditional level of moral thinking, hence, the school system needs to adopt policies and regulations to stress the importance of social orders. Conversely, learners are to be encouraged towards awareness and personal acceptance of the school community's norms rather than simply conforming to an externally imposed order. Learners get to understand and imbibe more moral values as they progress to higher grades within the school system. Learners in the upper grades should be encouraged to exercise greater responsibility for their own decisions while carefully measured opportunities should be provided to learners to behave based on voluntary responses to the school organization's expectations. Therefore, a high school's context or atmosphere should: 1) minimize pre-conventional moral reasoning (punishment-reward), 2) generally represent and encourage conventional moral thought (good order), and 3) provide learners with opportunities to react to and work at the level of principled reasoning. It is important to explain more carefully the processes, policies and procedures for establishing such an environment to the learners.

The teacher regardless of the materials, need to go beyond the information communicated within the learning contents to further ensure that learning experiences on moral values are exhibited freely by the learners in and outside the school system. The atmosphere or context in which learning happens and the expectations and feelings it expresses will be as relevant as the actual content of the learning activities in moral development. The work of Kohlberg, therefore, enjoins that moral development should provide the basis for a more complete understanding of the current situation and a context in which learners can be prepared to adopt solutions to recurrent or emerging problems. Kohlberg's theory significantly provides a stimulating challenge to learners' thoughts and perspectives from both theoretical aspects and practical applications that can be adopted in constantly changing contexts.

Literature Review

There is an outcry of social ills in South Africa, which are commonly found in schools and societies. The society is undergoing a serious moral breakdown in family and school values. Accordingly, Danso (2018) opines that this lack of morals and values which is evident in various forms of misdemeanours such as lack of discipline and self-control, violence, teenage pregnancy, high crime rates, promiscuity, vandalism in schools and suicide, is constantly reported by the media. Lilian, (2018) declares that moral bankruptcy can be addressed through the integration of values-based education in the school curricula. The important role of values integration in the teaching-learning process is crucial to address the phenomenon. This implies that teachers must accomplish the purpose of education which is not merely absorbing new knowledge and skills but more importantly, imbibing right values and attitudes (Evasco, 2015). Evasco (2015), further elucidates that teachers should begin by teaching the enduring, time-tested values of integrity, such as justice, respect for the rights of others and social responsibility to the learners. This implies that proper and intentional integration of these values in the curriculum will deliberately and systematically transform learners into responsive ones, who can absorb shocks from changes in the social environment, to adapt to complexity (Evasco, 2015).

Values are viewed as determiners of how people will live in harmony and peace without hurting one another, and become virtuous individuals within the community. Haydon (2004) avers that people live in a physical environment, where they co-habit and relate to one another; there is a need for an ethical environment to be ensured through values education. Hence, Values are to be inculcated into learners at their early ages in the school system to develop appropriate characters. These values are maintained during their adolescence to adulthood to appreciate themselves and others, and take full responsibility for their actions in the world around them. Integration of value-based education into the school system enhances a thought-provoking and engaging atmosphere for learners through the learning contents from the curriculum (Iyer, (2013). It is therefore significant to teachers to recognize the importance of integrating value-based education in learners to instil educational and cultural values that are necessary to achieve multi-faceted human growth that encompasses academic, physical, religious and ethical development. Thereby promoting holistic development of South African learners. It is believed that integration of values into the school curriculum as attributes of social life for learners will lead to collaboration, transparency, satisfaction, simplicity, solidarity, goodwill, reverence, compassion, empathy, integrity, modesty, and equality.

Sulayman (2014) posits that incorporating values-based education into the school curriculum is necessary to ensure that learners develop their constructive areas of strength while removing unworthy positions and behaviours. The premise is that learners steadily observe the habit of engaging in the spread of the positive in the process of value inclusion, unconsciously despising the poor and rejecting it. Indeed, from the point of view of incorporating the principles of moral teaching into the school curriculum, it eventually establishes a solid moral base that will ultimately motivate learners to resist unethical conduct, including present and potential general corruption. Durdukoca (2019) agrees with Sulayman (2013) that educational principles in schools are aimed at helping learners to strengthen their social tendencies by embracing social and universal values that can foster their character. Also, Durdukoca (2019) in his longitudinal study conducted in Turkey, avers that values education is offered in Turkish schools with the formal curricula in both primary and secondary schools in the teaching-learning process of all courses/subjects. Seemingly, Akbaş (2009) avows that the inclusion of values education in the curriculum will ensure that learners can consistently acquire specific moral values through different teaching methods, different subjects and techniques. Moreover, for teachers to succeed in the tasks of integrating values into learners, they need to display and act as both participants and coaches in values education in the classroom. This implies that teachers must model and exhibit the same values they want to advocate in practice. Hence, the exhibited values by the teachers inside and outside the classroom will be easy for learners to emulate. Extant literature also shows that teachers cannot remain neutral in the teaching of their subjects without consciously integrating some values into learners (Sulayman, 2013; Evasco, 2015; Durdukoca, 2019). There is more to teaching profession than just facilitation of learning experiences but also moulding of characters with appropriate societal values. Teachers should therefore be responsible to encourage and teach their learners moral values at every opportunity. This

is an acceptable philosophy that can strengthen the moral education in building learners' positive behaviours which can positively influence them in school and later in life.

Similarly, Nurdin (2015) affirms that the integration and implementation of values education are influenced by the commitment, the quality of teachers and their teaching methods. Though, Nurdin (2015) identifies some challenges to values integration in the school curriculum to include teachers' lack of adequate and necessary skills, the irrelevant curriculum that tends to focus on values argumentation rather than the strategy to grow the values on the learners. Kenan (2009) avers that there are significant social and moral harms to contemporary society that have never existed before, which contribute to the deterioration of families and the declining state of civic culture in the present age. He further posits that effective educational values inherent in the curriculum require an adequate plan to ensure that both teachers and learners benefit from the value-laden curriculum. Seemingly, Sutrop, et al. (2013) affirms that learners must be able to exhibit values as a way of understanding and conceptualizing values education. Moreover, Sutrop, et al. (2013) agree that learners' exhibition of values will enable them to deal with the higher qualities of human experience. Learning moral values in schools make values to be consciously learnt as a mechanical way of addressing social vices, and to enrich the learners. Imperatively, incorporating moral principles is of great benefit to learners as it will train them to be responsible members of society (Kowino et al., 2012; Ilechukwu & Ugwuozor, 2014). The integration of moral values in the school curriculum will promote moral judgment, creativity and reasoning of children. Also, good moral judgment will assist learners to responsibly respond to academic matters rather than participating in disciplinary cases for wrong behaviour in realizing their academic dreams. Expressively, Brady (2011) notes that while the integration of values education revolves around the role of teachers, the impact of their values, influence on learners and how they express these values in the classrooms are consistently overlooked in values education.

Integration of Values Education is capable of correcting learners with repellent habits, attitudes or behaviours. Grieshaber and McArdle (2014) assert that teachers need to develop effective strategies that can correct or remodel learners who display inappropriate behavioural actions, attitudes or habits. Teachers' use of diverse approaches in inculcating values in learners through teaching and learning activities enhance the integration of values in schools explicitly or implicitly. To incorporate principles of moral education into learners, teachers may adopt mentoring of learners. Similarly, Chowdhury (2016) suggests various teaching methods such as role-playing, drama, simulation, educational games, debate, conversation, ventures, community work, educational visits, interviews and brainstorming to facilitate moral and character values. Chaitanya (2017) agrees with Kohlberg's view of moral examples where teachers' most important duty is to be role models, which enables the learners to effectively grasp with appropriate societal values.

Method

Research design is a researcher's strategy of how to do a particular study from identifying a problem, writing research questions, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, and report writing (Creswell, 2014). It is also the road map that a researcher decides to follow during the research journey to find answers to the research questions as validly, objectively, accurately, and economically as possible (Kumar, 2014). The researchers, therefore, adopted phenomenology to explore the experiences, feelings and sentiments of the teachers who are participants in this study. This study was qualitative in its approach to understand the phenomenon. The phenomenological design of the study adequately described the meaning of this experience both in terms of what was experienced and how it was experienced (Teherani, et al. 2015) to effectively address the research objectives. The study was situated at King Cetshwayo District, one of the eleven district municipalities within KwaZulu-Natal province as the study area. Purposive sampling was used to select ten lesson observations from five different schools and a semi-structured interview with five teachers each from selected five schools in King Cetshwayo District. A total of 25 teachers participated in this project.

According to Creswell (2014:90), "an observation schedule is an instrument for gathering data; it relies on a researcher's seeing things and recording these observations, rather than relying on subjects' self-report responses to questions or statements". The observations allowed the researcher to see a phenomenon from a different angle and enhanced the research outcome of the study. According to Bertram and Christiansen (2010), who strongly support the idea of triangulating interviews with observations, there are no doubt teachers who often teach in different ways to how they *say* they teach. Thus including classroom observations, this will enable the researcher to see what is happening in a classroom. Thus, a total of ten (10) participants who were teachers in high schools were engaged in classroom observations. The purposive sampling ensured that a variety of schools and contexts were involved for diverse perspectives to the phenomenon (McMillan & Schumacher, 2010). Content analysis of the data collected from the observation tool was done thematically to present findings for discussion. All ethical considerations for this approved study were duly adhered with. Permissions were granted by the district Department of Education, the heads of their departments, and the principals to access the participants for the study. Though, this paper forms part of a bigger project that adopted many data instruments such as semi-structured interview, document analysis and classroom observations; thus, the data instrument for this paper was observation tool for classroom observation of the participants.

Results and Discussion

The presentation and discussion of findings presented below have been thematically analysed to answer the research questions. According to Creswell (2014) analysis of data is to generate meanings, which are results of the systematic arrangement and presentation of the information, the information is organised to show comparisons, contrasts and insights that can be established by the researchers. Ten classroom observations in five different schools and semi-structured interview have been thematically analysed to present the results for this study.

The Conceptualisation of Values Education

The conceptualisation of values education refers to the participants' understanding of what values education is all about. Participants were observed in their classroom teaching on how they explicitly transmit or integrate values to learners using their teaching subjects as vehicles to convey and inculcate morals to learners. Classroom observations showed that few of the participants did not understand the concept of values education as a result they could not integrate it in the course of their teaching appropriately. To them, the main purpose of education and teaching was to develop the cognitive domain of learners only without much consideration of the affective domain. If ever values were taught, they were only taught implicitly or unintentionally as this was evident during the classroom observations. From the classroom observations and analysis of their lesson plans, core values were absent from the majority of the participants' classroom practices. Thus, since they were not reflected on their lesson plans these teachers did not intentionally plan or prepare for nurturing of values during their classroom practice. Furthermore, the absence of alignment of values with the lesson objectives, theme and the subject was evident to show that some of the participants did not understand the concept. A probe further showed that they were not sure if the Curriculum Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS) documents explicitly outline the deliberate and intentional teaching of learners with knowledge, skills, values and attitudes. Their understanding of the concept was also expressed in the interviews.

Excerpts

"Talking of these values in my subject, I always emphasise that they need to study, not to copy, during the exam or the assessment, I even go as far as providing them with the answer sheets rather than their coming with their answer sheets. But generally, this is what we normally talk about, maybe for about five minutes, because there is always a need to talk about them. Yes, some of them can take what you are saying as an adviser to them, but some of them can't. It all depends on what

they are saying at home, what the parents are saying. If the learner is familiar with whatever I'm saying as a parent in front of him or her in the class, then it will work in my favour as a teacher and that of other learners as well." (TC1)

On the conceptualisation of values education, another participant had this to say:

"I think values education has to do with how a person needs to behave in a particular society or anywhere in the world since the values are common.

Value A can be found in one country, and the same value is also applicable to another country, so I think it's what is acceptable to society as a whole." (TB2)

It is of concern that this study reveals that teachers are generally not familiar with the concept for them to consciously apply it in their daily classroom practice, and how it should be integrated into the curriculum:

"Even though I don't remember clearly which statement it is in the CAPS document, there is a statement that stresses moral values when learners are given a scenario that a CEO maybe has used money intended for the business for himself, and that is recorded as a business expense, but is unethical. So we've got those words in my subject which mean the CAPS document does have them, even though (if I can put it in a percentage) it could be like ten per cent of statements in the CAPS policy that have to do with values." (TB1)

Findings revealed that the participants failed to understand that the South African post-apartheid curriculum focuses on the re-orientation of learners for societal values that pride them as democratic citizens. It was also evident that the participants were uncertain as to how the policy intends to integrate values education into the curriculum. Teaching values in schools is not a choice. CAPS states categorically that the purpose of the curriculum implementation is to equip learners irrespective of their socio-economic background, race, gender, physical ability with the knowledge, skills and values necessary to self-fulfilment, and meaningful participation in society as citizens of a free county (Department of Education, 2011). Findings, therefore, clearly indicated that some of the teachers were not even aware of the CAPS advocacy for the integration of values education.

Planning and Nurturing Values Education

This theme relates to the planning and nurturing of values education in the classroom by the teachers. It is the responsibility of a teacher to successfully interact with learners in creating a positive classroom atmosphere. Findings from the classroom observations indicated that the planning and nurturing of values education are integrated into classroom practices unintentionally by some participants, while some participants observed their learners while practising or exhibiting certain values. Excerpts from the interview showed that some teachers specifically taught learners some values they needed to know:

"I think we teach them during the learning process because we don't have a time that's specifically allocated for this self-control, honestly, but we teach them during a learning process because it depending on what they are doing. So you just apply it on towards their behaviour that they are doing at that moment" (TB4).

Interestingly, one of the participants indicated the use of role-playing in drama as one of the means of nurturing his learners to learn values:

"I think isiZulu can do drama to show values and tell stories." (TD5)

Another participant also indicated the use of role-playing to teach learners values:

"In literature, for example, we use the characters that we meet as we generally discuss values in literature, so we pick out some of these values and show them that these characters possess both good and the bad values. Then they take it from there." (TC4)

One of the participants remarked that even though values education is specifically enlisted in the curriculum for his subject, yet he ensured that learners learn values through some activities in the class:

“Some of them have nothing to do with the curriculum, for example, always keeping your classroom clean. They always know that when I come in I look down on the floor immediately. They remember they are supposed to pick up papers before I even say a word, but when I find the classroom clean I make a point of commending them, and that usually makes them happy. And sometimes if somebody who is usually out of uniform shows up in clean full uniform I make a point of noting it, or if performance has been good I make the others cheer them up, or maybe ask them to stand up so that they understand that school is a good thing. And if everybody appreciates what they do it gives them a sense of pride, and therefore others want to emulate that one way or the other, so that someday they also get the praise of a class, at least for that day.” (TE5)

Classroom observations in the sample schools showed that values were being imparted to the learners intentionally in some specific subjects, while in others, a minority of the learners were taught values unintentionally. In a school, during the classroom observation of Accounting, the learners could not display the value of cleanliness as the classroom was dirty, and the teacher was not bothered. However, in the same school, during the Economics class, the classroom was cleaned-up before the arrival of the teacher. Similar observations were noticed in other schools where values such as respect, social responsibility, health and hygiene were exhibited during the lessons, while in some schools they were ignored.

Miller and Pedro (2006) claim that a respectful and conducive classroom atmosphere leads to a greater understanding of and appreciation for the diverse population in a school community. Chowdhury (2016) argues that to improve the moral and character values, multiple teaching techniques such as role-playing, drama, simulation, educational games, debate, discussion, projects, group work, educational visitation, interview and brainstorming might be implemented. It is imperative that there should be a nexus between teachers' expectations and learners' achievements, so teachers should be willing to assist learners with necessary help, attention and feedback in classrooms (McConnell & Elliot, 2003). Hence, it is critical that teachers purposefully plan and carefully integrate values into their learners during their classroom practices (Ngussa, Makewa & Allida 2016; Ajani & Govender, 2018).

The Pedagogy of Values Education

Some of the participants struggled with the conceptualisation of values education during the semi-structured interviews. This was also evident during the classroom observations, as only a few of the participants planned, nurtured or attempted to integrate the teaching of values in their classroom practice consciously. Most of the participants did not clearly understand how to teach values. It became obvious that they were using a conventional pedagogical approach which was based on the banking model of education, which emphasizes the content instead of the learners. The review of some extant Literature indicated that teaching values are about teaching the learners how to think, reflect, critique, evaluate and appreciate one's values, and those of others; to develop better communication skills and make better decisions that can be exhibited in their behaviour and actions (Hadi, 2015; Chaitanya, 2017). This view is emphasised in the Manifesto on Values, where De Klerk (2003) states emphatically that values education is not a simple one-dimensional issue. It involves reflection, decision making, purposeful conduct, the moulding of good habits over time, and the building of character.

Teachers need to note that values and skills cannot be developed in learners only by forcing them to memorise words or information. Opportunities must be provided to internalise such attitudes and values so that they can be sustained in the long run. It was observed in one of the schools, (school D) where a participant (TD5) attempted to use storytelling during an isiZulu class to integrate values. Indeed, in this school, literature was taught in the form of role-playing, where learners were role-playing the characters in the story. The whole process of teaching through role-playing revolved around acting out the story, depicting and miming certain values. However, whether these learners were effectively able to internalise and reflect on these values is debatable; as the crucial need here is a reflection through which attitudes change and

growth in values occurs. It is critical that teachers explicitly understand the meaning and significance of values education, and what approaches they can use to integrate it into their classroom practices across the curriculum. Chaitanya (2017) elucidates that values education does not mean value imposition or value indoctrination, but to teach learners what is good and worthwhile in their culture and can be preserved. He strongly believes that values education can transform a confused and unhealthy mind into a fresh, young, innocent, vibrant, natural and attentive mind. If teachers are not explicitly and purposefully teaching values while imparting information and knowledge to learners, they will remain confused as to what is good and worth doing in the society; thus there is a need for the appropriate and effective pedagogy to integrate values.

Conversely, most subject contents enable teachers to use the questioning technique as observed in the classroom observations with the participants. However, most of these questions were lower cognitive, as their focus was simply on imparting factual knowledge. However, some of the participants did not use the questions to inculcate values or alert learners about appropriate behaviour and attitudes that can be exhibited in and out of the school system. According to Miliband (2004), quality education is possible when curriculum and pedagogy interact and support the learning of values in deliberate and meaningful ways to the learners. Teachers play an important role in making this happen. From the above findings, it is evident that there is a gap between these critical elements of curriculum, pedagogy and values.

The Classroom Environment

This theme attempts to establish whether the physical environment of the classrooms communicates certain values that can facilitate or hinder the development of values intended by the teacher. In some of the sampled schools where classroom observations were carried out, learners showed respect and dignity by greeting the researchers with admiration. Miller and Pedro (2006) assert that the classroom environment should always be characterised by the demonstration of respect, dignity, courtesy, individuality and uniqueness. Seating arrangements, uniform, cleanliness, positive communication, a conducive, non-threatening atmosphere and the general behaviour in some of these schools indicated that values were integrated into the classroom environment. Furthermore, Haghighi and Jusan (2012) posit that modification of learners' seating arrangements in the classroom is an approach to control disruptive behaviour in the class environment. Seemingly, silent sitting has also been considered an important strategy which helps in the habit of maintaining a conducive classroom, strengthening the inner being or self, consolidating information received and retaining what is essential. This strategy could be observed in some schools visited, but in other schools, chaotic situations were the order of the day.

Subject-related charts, and classroom rules highlighting punctuality, respect and caring for other learners and their property displayed on the walls in some of the observed schools. Although teachers thought that they did not have relevant information to support them in teaching values, one could deduce that they were rather unconscious that the classroom environment had elements of values which could be transmitted to learners implicitly, not through teaching. Contrary to the ideal classroom environment that the researchers observed, the above attributes in some of the schools used for classroom observations were absent. For instance, teaching was taking place in classrooms that were not conducive to teaching and learning; the classrooms were dirty with papers scattered all over the floor; desks were not orderly arranged; there was no evidence of classroom rules, and learners were ill-disciplined, shouting at each other, and at times showing disrespect to the teachers and other learners. Therefore, the classroom observations showed that the classroom environment can either promote or hamper the development of values in learners.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this study was to investigate how teachers integrate values education in high schools. The importance of values in education is illustrated by the fact that the youth, mainly those from developing countries such as South Africa and other African countries, live in societies where violence, crime and racial intolerance are rife. In this context, teachers concluded that it is their responsibility to integrate values

education into the curriculum to shape learners' lives in society. Different values as enshrined in the South African Manifesto on Values must be inculcated in learners to transform their lives so that they become responsible and acceptable citizens in their societies. Participants stated that all subjects can be used to convey values to learners.

Findings also indicated that role modelling of values by both teachers and parents is an important instrument to be used at school and at home for learners to be able to emulate acceptable values such as respect, honesty, caring, Ubuntu, love and many others. Teachers are imitated a lot by learners, and the need for their proper conduct at all times is crucial. However, there is an obvious and alarming decline of values both in the schools and in the society at large. Although the study was limited to five schools, findings from the interviews and classroom observation revealed a gap between policymakers and teachers. This gap is associated with the teachers' lack of understanding of the concept of values in education. From the responses given in the interviews with the participants, it was clear that some of them did not even understand the concept of values education. As a result, they could not teach what they did not know. It was also clear that for them the main purpose of teaching was only to develop the cognitive domain of learners. If ever values were taught, they were only taught implicitly or unintentionally.

Recommendations

The integration of values education in the school system is important to South African learners, as it will address growing moral decadence in the global society. The study, therefore, provides some useful recommendations to promote the integration of values in learners. The following recommendations are pertinent for the school management teams, teachers, education policymakers, parents and all other stakeholders in the education system:

- Existing policies on teaching and learning of values education in schools should be reviewed by curriculum specialists to integrate values education into all the school subjects.
- The Department of Basic Education should provide regular and adequate training on pedagogical content knowledge for effective integration of values education in learners.
- Teachers should be involved in the design of curriculum content for values education to enhance the regular integration of values into classroom practices.
- There is a need for the school management team, teachers and parents to work together to integrate and inculcate values education. Parents should cooperate with the schools to complement schools' effort on the integration of values education.
- Learners who display or exhibit good morals/values should be recognised, rewarded and celebrated as models to their fellow learners. The schools should design engagements or activities that can promote these in learners.
- Mentoring of learners by the teachers should be encouraged as a good way of nurturing learners in acceptable norms of society. It can be used to correct learners' bad behaviour.
- The classroom environment can either promote or hamper the development of values in learners. It is therefore suggested that teachers and school management teams create a school environment that will be conducive to attracting to and creating in the minds of school learners the aesthetic values that can gradually be part of their lives.
- It is suggested that both pre-service and in-service teachers be exposed to and explicitly groomed in various social values and the significance of integrating them into their classroom practice.

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